

Bradford HDRC Policy Brief

Bridging the Digital Divide - Preparing Children and Young People for Digital Futures
Target Audience: Local Authorities

Based on N8 Child of the North Report - An evidence-based plan for for upskilling our children and young people for digital futures
CotN_Digital futures_Report_7.pdf

Key Evidence Based Messages

- **Digital access and digital skills are essential to enabling people to fully participate in our society.** They support success in education, getting good jobs, social life and access to goods and services essential to daily living.
- **There is a digital divide.** The poorest groups in our society lack digital access and skills. This deepens educational inequalities, economic inequalities and prevents access to goods and services essential for everyday living.
- **National level focus:**
 - Establish a “minimum digital living standards” framework.
 - Promote digital inclusion in schools through continuing professional development of teachers.
 - Create a national Digital Creativity Skills Commons.
- **Local level focus:**
 - Ensure access to broadband and equipment.
 - Develop partnerships across public, voluntary and community sectors to leverage in resources, expertise and support.
 - Develop digital literacy and skills.
 - Enhance school curriculums and teacher Continuing Professional Development (CPD).
 - Work with communities to develop local projects.
 - Build on approaches trialled in practice, highlighted in this briefing.

The Problem: Digital Exclusion and The Digital Divide

2 in 5 young people have no broadband or laptop/computer access

3 in 4 young people feel they lack the digital skills to thrive

2 in 5 people lack essential digital skills for daily life

Digital skills shortages are estimated to cost the economy £65 billion per year. By 2030, 5 million workers will lack the digital skills necessary for the workplace. Digital access and skills are essential to enabling people to fully participate in our society: essential to success in education, getting good jobs, social life and securing access to goods and services.

What you can do at a local level

- **Develop local “minimum” digital living standards frameworks.** This can bring together partners across public, private, voluntary and community sectors to focus policy on the digital infrastructure needed to fully participate in today’s digital world, e.g., access to high-speed broadband, a functioning computer or laptop, and essential digital skills training.
- **Support development of digital literacy and educational skills programmes** across local areas and in schools
- **Develop partnerships across sectors to leverage in resources, expertise and support.** This may include mentorships, training, internships, workshops, provision of equipment and training programmes.
- **Work with local communities to identify local needs and develop projects and programmes** in community settings.
- **Work with schools to extend and enhance the IT curriculum and support development of teachers’ IT skills.**
- **Build on approaches featured below.**

Approaches trialled in practice

Example	Approach	Impact
Digital Inclusion Living Well Schools	District Digital inclusion programme created to ensure children and families in need can access the technology and skills to engage in the digital world. A Digital Inclusion Officer supports schools and families.	Ensure access to basic digital resources.
Robotics in the Classroom	Uses affordable machines designed to support learning through interactive and practical exercises.	Teach digital skills. Develop wider skills such as team working. Support development of schools as inclusive environments.
Impact Gamers CLC BAFTA-winning non-profit community interest company	Uses gaming to engage CYP aged 8-16 and teach foundational skills. Offers free after-school sessions in game coding. Runs in schools and community settings.	Develop IT skills and build confidence, self-esteem, and social skills.
White Rose Centre for Inclusive Computing – collaboration of three universities alongside STEM Learning and its National Centre for Computing Education	Supports initiatives aimed at enhancing inclusion in the tech sector e.g. STEM Learning’s National Centre for Computing Education runs the I-Belong programme, a flagship campaign to change girls’ perceptions of computing.	Transform the perception and accessibility of computing education and careers.
The Leeds Institute for Data Analytics (LIDA)	Launched the Open Data Science for Schools (LODSS) initiative in 2022. Delivers activities that develop students’ digital skills while also tackling challenges, such as low aspiration, poor food security, and a lack of awareness around healthy eating.	Narrow the digital skills gap for young people in areas of acute socioeconomic inequality.
Living Well Schools: A Partnership between University, LA, public services and VCS	Frames digital divide as a public health problem. Uses digital platform and profiling to assess school needs and connect with health and wellbeing services; runs a Digital Inclusion Programme – to bridge digital skill gaps.	Ensure CYP and families in need can access the technology and skills to engage in the digital world.